

Nutrient Adsorption onto Modified Biochar for Stormwater Treatment

A. H. M. F. Anwar* and B. Chen**

*School of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, Curtin University, Perth, Western Australia
(Email: f.anwar@curtin.edu.au)

**School of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, Curtin University, Perth, Western Australia
(Email: cloudchen6@126.com)

Abstract

Nitrogen ($\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) and phosphorus ($\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$) species are known to be the major dissolved contaminants in stormwater runoff. In this research, a series of batch experiments were conducted to remove nutrients from stormwater using raw and modified biochar with varying initial concentration (1-5mg/L), dosage (2-10g) and pH (4.3-6.5). The raw biochar was modified using NaOH. The results revealed that the removal efficiency was improved using modified biochar by 50%, 10%, 10% and 70% for $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, and $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ respectively. Maximum removal was obtained using modified biochar as 92% $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, 40% $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and 100% removal of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ and $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ was obtained. The effect of adsorbent dosage and initial concentration was found significant on nutrient adsorption, but pH has insignificant impact. The adsorption isotherm study found Freundlich model explaining the adsorption process better. The adsorption kinetics were studied using intraparticle diffusion, and a pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model. Most of the kinetic results with modified biochar were found supporting the two-stage intraparticle diffusion. The adsorption data revealed that the pseudo-second order model describes nutrient adsorption better. Modified biochar was found suitable for use in the biochar-augmented bio-filtration system for stormwater treatment.

Keywords: Adsorption; biochar; modified; nutrient; stormwater; treatment

INTRODUCTION

Stormwater runoff typically contains sediments, trash, heavy metal, nutrients and various pollutants from sewer overflows, septic tank leaks, animal faeces, building and construction sites. These pre-existed contaminants can cause (i) the reduction in plant growth (ii) the damage to biodiversity, (iii) the excessive growth of aquatic weeds and algae (iv) the increase in pH (v) high toxicity to fish and other aquatic lives and (vi) the severe toxicity to human health. To protect the environmental resources and human health, water sensitive urban design (WSUD) is used in Australia for urban development. These processes use physical, biological and chemical techniques which use sand filters, infiltration basins and trenches, rain gardens, bioretention ponds, seasonal ponds (dry and wet ponds), constructed wetlands, filter strips, swales, wet vaults, biochar filter and underground sedimentation practices. Among the stormwater contaminants, nutrients such as phosphorus ($\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$) and nitrogen species ($\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$) are the primary pollutants that exist in wastewater or stormwater runoff (Sizmur et al., 2017). The excessive presence of these nutrients enhances the growth of algal bloom (known as eutrophication) in water bodies (lakes, wetlands, streams, rivers or coastal waters). With the decomposition of algae, bacteria grow and depletes the amount of dissolved oxygen in water and thus threatens the aquatic lives. It is therefore an essential step to control the excessive amount of nutrients in waterbody for sustainable ecosystems.

The removal of nutrients may be either biological process (i.e., nitrification or denitrification) or the physical process such as adsorption. Among the many methods (reverse osmosis, electro dialysis, activated carbon adsorption and adsorption by green media) used for nutrients removal, adsorption method was found most cost-effective and environment friendly. Other researchers used low-cost green media including tree bark, wood chips, wheat straw, tire crumbs, sawdust, alfalfa, mulch compost, paper, cotton, and sulfur/limestone (Kim et al 2003; Xuan et al., 2010). Harmayani and Anwar (2016) used radiata pine sawdust and found 100% removal of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$. Iqbal et al., (2015) found biochar as an effective adsorption medium. The formation of biochar was found due to the investigation of application in lignocellulosic biomass, which was extracted from rice husk, bean straw, corn stalk, and sawdust (Liu et al., 2015). During the typical process of

thermochemical decomposition pyrolysis, lignocellulosic biomass was under anoxic conditions at different heating rates, and it generates a solid residue called biochar. The biochar has proven to be a good adsorbent because of its microporous structure and high cation exchange capacity. Recently, Alam and Anwar (2020) used *Eucalyptus Wandoo* (EW) biochar and alum sludge to remove nutrients and found EW biochar could remove NO₂-N and NH₃-N significantly while the alum sludge could remove PO₄-P significantly. However, EW biochar was unable to remove PO₄-P. Sizmur et al. (2017) has reported that the efficiency of pollutant removal using biochar could be significantly improved if biochar surface properties are chemically modified (e.g., functional groups, porosity, temperature). Takaya et al., (2016) used modified biochar with chemical and surface activation by metal chloride salts, KOH and H₂O₂ to remove PO₄-P and found the removal capacity improved from low levels (2.1-3.6%) to high levels (66.4-70.3%). The objective of this paper is to investigate the improvement capacity of modified farmchar biochar with NaOH to remove nutrients (NH₃-N, NO₂-N, NO₃-N, and PO₄-P) from stormwater. The adsorption isotherm and kinetics were also studied. The results will be useful for water managers to design efficient water infrastructures for maintaining the water quality in urban waterways.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Synthetic stormwater

The stock solutions of nutrients (NH₃-N, NO₃-N, NO₂-N and PO₄-P) were prepared from KNO₃, NH₄Cl, H₂NaO₄P and NaNO₂ respectively. The synthetic stormwater containing all nutrient concentrations (1-5mg/l) were prepared using deionised water. The pH of the solution was adjusted (pH=4.3-6.5) using NaOH and HCl.

Biochar and Modified biochar

The feedstock of biochar was collected from farmchar supplied by Energy Farmer Australia. The biochar was smashed into small particles using hammer and was sieved for suitable particle sizes of <300 µm, 300–600 µm, 600 µm–1.18 mm, 1.18–2.36 mm, and >2.36 mm, respectively. The sieved biochar was washed several times with distilled water to remove any possible pollutants. Next, the sieved biochar was soaked in NaOH solution (2mg/L) for 24 hrs and the biochar-to-solution ratio was 0.1 g/ml. The samples were washed with deionized water until they reach a neutral pH. Then the treated biochar was oven dried at 180 °C for 12 hours.

Experiments

A series of batch experiments were conducted using raw and modified biochar with varying nutrient concentrations (1-5mg/L), dosage (2-10g) and pH (4.3-6.5). The biochar of specific dosage was mixed with 250mL of synthetic stormwater in an Erlenmeyer flask, wrapped with parafilm and kept onto a 16-flask capacity shaking platform at 100 rpm. A 2 mL water sample from the batch was taken at predetermined time interval until it reached equilibrium. The samples were filtered in a filter syringe of 0.45µm and analysed for nutrient concentration using AQUAKEM 200 water analyser (Labmedics Analytical Solutions) (±0.015–0.02).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Removal efficiency

The effect of initial concentration, dosage and pH was investigated on the removal efficiency of different nutrients for raw and modified biochar. The results with varying initial concentration are presented in Fig. 1. The maximum NH₃-N removals of modified biochar were increased to 60% from 30%, NO₂-N removals 40% from 15%, NO₃-N removals to 80% from 30% and PO₄-P removals to 50% from 5% when 2g of dosage was used (Fig. 1). Considering all results, maximum removal was found 92% for NH₃-N, 40% for NO₂-N and 100% for NO₃-N and PO₄-P respectively. However, the modification of biochar improved the overall removal efficiency of these nutrients

within 10-70%. This is because of greater surface area, porosity and functional groups of modified biochar that was obtained during the modification process. However, the contact time achieving the maximum removal efficiency varied between the raw and modified biochar. The removal efficiency was found to be lower at higher initial concentration which is similar to other study (Harmayani and Anwar, 2016). Higher initial concentration contains more adsorbate within the solution while the available sorption site on biochar surface is limited. The removal efficiency was found increasing with dosage because of increased sorption sites but it was found significantly higher for modified biochar. It was improved by 50% for NH₃-N removal and 70% for PO₄-P removal when modified biochar was used. The effect of pH on the nutrient removal was found insignificant but significant removal was obtained with modified biochar for all pH ranges (results not shown here).

Adsorption Isotherm

The adsorption isotherm for raw and modified biochar was investigated using Langmuir and Freundlich model. The Langmuir model assumes adsorption occurring on monolayer of the adsorbent surface and the same sites. Freundlich model analyses the adsorption by assuming that the adsorption takes place on multilayer on adsorbent surface and different sites., therefore, they carry different levels of energy on adsorption site. The results of varying initial concentrations revealed that most of the nutrient adsorption follows Freundlich model suggesting multilayer adsorption for modified biochar. The adsorption intensity with various initial concentrations for modified biochar was calculated following Anwar and Harmayani (2016) and the results revealed that the adsorption of modified biochar showed more favourable in lower concentration except NO₂-N adsorption.

Adsorption Kinetics

Adsorption kinetics were investigated using Intraparticle diffusion model and pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model (Alam and Anwar 2020). Intraparticle diffusion model is an appropriate analysis to distinguish between the kinetic and the diffusion rate control. Intraparticle diffusion was studied using Eq (1) where the amount of adsorption q_t ($\mu\text{g/g}$) is plotted with $t^{0.5}$ (t is contact time):

$$q_t = k_{di}t^{0.5} + Z_i \quad (1)$$

where k_{di} ($\text{mg/g h}^{0.5}$) is the intraparticle diffusion rate constant of stage i which is the slope of Eq 1 and the Z_i is the intercept of stage i . Linear plot showing the straight line describes the process solely controlled by Intraparticle diffusion. If it shows two straight lines with two different slopes, it indicates two different adsorption processes. The first stage shows the surface adsorption onto the solid surface and the second stage describes the diffusion onto the adsorption site. The results revealed that the adsorption occurred mostly in two stages. For NH₃-N, NO₂-N and NO₃-N

Fig 1. Effect of initial concentration (1-5mg/L) on nutrient removal for raw and modified biochar for 2g of dosage.

adsorption, the initial steep stage shows that the diffusion on modified biochar surface occurred in first three minutes, the second less steep phase represents gradual adsorption as intraparticle diffusion was occurring within the pores. For PO₄-P adsorption, the adsorption in dosage of 2g and 5g produced two stages but produced one stage for higher dosage such as 8 and 10g. Increasing dosage leads to a gradually higher diffusion rate occurring on modified biochar surface for PO₄-P adsorption. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model was applied for the adsorption data on modified biochar and found pseudo-second order model is more appropriate describing the behaviour of adsorption kinetics under the effect of dosage, initial concentration and pH for all nutrients.

The overall results indicate that the farmchar biochar modified with NaOH can be used as an effective adsorbent to remove nitrogen and phosphorous from water. The use of this modified biochar could effectively reduce the landfill load for waste management and improve the water quality of waterbodies receiving stormwater.

CONCLUSION

The nutrient (NH₃-N, NO₂-N, NO₃-N and PO₄-P) adsorption onto the raw and NaOH-modified biochar was investigated in batches for treating the stormwater. The results revealed that nutrient removal efficiency was improved significantly with modified biochar. Maximum removal was found 92% for NH₃-N, 40% for NO₂-N and 100% for NO₃-N and PO₄-P respectively. The modification of biochar improved the removal efficiency of NH₃-N, NO₂-N, NO₃-N and PO₄-P by 50%, 10%, 10% and 70% respectively. The kinetic results showed that the nitrogen adsorption followed two-stage intraparticle diffusion indicating surface adsorption in first stage and diffusion control in second stage. But the kinetics of phosphorous adsorption followed the two-stage process for lower dosage and one-stage for higher dosage indicating higher surface adsorption with higher dosage. The pseudo-second order model was found describing the nutrient adsorption onto modified biochar better and Freundlich model fitted better than Langmuir indicating multi-layer adsorption takes place when modified biochar is used. This makes the modified biochar a suitable adsorbent for treating stormwater using low impact development such as rain garden, swales and/or bioretention systems. However, column experiment is suggested before putting into the actual sites to understand the dynamic behavior for nutrient adsorption onto the modified biochar.

REFERENCES

- Alam, M. Z., Anwar, A. H. M. F., (2020). Nutrients adsorption onto biochar and alum sludge for treating stormwater. *J of Water and Environment Technology*, 18 (2): 132-146.
- Harmayani, K. D., Anwar, A. H. M. F., (2016). Adsorption kinetics and equilibrium study of nitrogen species onto radiata pine (*Pinus radiata*) sawdust, *Water Sci. & Technol.*, 74(2): 402-415.
- Iqbal H, Garcia-Perez M, Flury M (2015). Effect of biochar on leaching of organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus from compost in bioretention systems. *Sci. of the Total Environ.*, 521, 37-45.
- Kim, H., Seagren, E.A., Davis, A. P., (2003): Engineered bioretention for removal of nitrate from stormwater runoff. *Water Environ. Res.*, 75 (4), 355–367, 2003.
- Liu, W.-J., Jiang, H., & Yu, H.-Q. (2015). Development of Biochar-Based Functional Materials: Toward a Sustainable Platform Carbon Material. *Chemical Reviews*, 115(22), 12251-12285.
- Sizmur, T., Fresno, T., Akgül, G., Frost, H., Moreno-Jiménez, E. (2017). Biochar modification to enhance sorption of inorganics from water. *Bioresource Technology*, 246, 34-47.
- Takaya, C. A., Fletcher, L. A., Singh, S., Okwuosa, U. C., Ross, A. B., (2016). Recovery of phosphate with chemically modified biochars. *J of Environ. Chem. Engineering*, 4(1), 1156-1165.
- Xuan, Z., Chang, N., Wanielista, M., Hossain, F., (2010). Laboratory-scale Characterization of a green sorption medium for on-site sewage treatment and disposal to improve nutrient removal. *Environ. Eng. Sci.* 27 (4), 301–312, 2010.